

OPTIMIZING OF CULTURE MEDIUM FOR *Sporosarcina pasteurii* AS BIOCEMENTING AGENT BY USING WHEY

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Population growth and the consequent rise in the need for investment on civil infrastructures have made inevitable to use novel and cost-effective building materials and techniques with lower environmental effects (DeJong et al., 2010). Cement production process (as a widely used material in the civil projects) is accomplished with about 8% of CO₂ emission (Wong, 2015). To reduce the effects of CO₂ emissions, there is an alternative solution that is environmentally friendly by utilizing living things called biocementation. Bio-cementation is a technique that uses microorganisms to produce calcium carbonate for construction purpose. Through microbiologically induced calcium carbonate precipitation (MICP), microorganisms can react with chemical components to produce minerals in the form of organic-inorganic compounds acting as a binding agent (Prozorov, 2015). In order to increase the compressive strength of cement composites, MICP has been thoroughly investigated utilizing a variety of microorganism species. Microbially induced calcite precipitation (MICP) refers to the formation of calcium carbonate in the presence of the different metabolic activities of microorganisms, including urealysis, photosynthesis, denitrification, ammonification, sulfate reduction and methane oxidation (Anbu et al., 2016 ; Zhu et al., 2014). The *Bacillus* species that has been investigated the most is *Sporosarcina pasteurii*. *S. pasteurii* are urease-producing bacteria that have the ability to induce sufficient calcium carbonate precipitation for bio-cementation to occur in concrete structures and the mechanism is influenced by urea hydrolysis (Bundur et al., 2017). Under proper conditions, *S. pasteurii* can produce urease to decompose urea into carbonate and ammonia. The resulted carbonate reacts with calcium ions, forming the calcite (calcium carbonate) precipitation (Gorospe et al., 2013; Launchnor et al., 2015). *S. pasteurii* and bacterially produced γ -polyglutamate (PGA) solution were applied to produce nacre-inspired layered calcium carbonate-polyglutamate composite materials that exhibited high extensibility and stiffness (Spiesz et al., 2019). Apart from that, the cultivation of *S. pasteurii* requires high-cost production and treatment complexity on a large scale, so to reduce those obstacles, there is an alternative solution in optimizing culture media by utilizing organic waste. This alternative solution is promising with its low cost and eco-friendly technology for environmental biocementation for large-scale applications.

Previous research used cementation solutions as culture media to cultivate *S. pasteurii* in the biocementation process. A rare, large-scale use of organic material or waste to substitute cementation solutions such as nutrient broth, nutrient agar, urea, and calcium chloride. Beside, isolation media also consist of GPA, YEA dan PDA (Periadnadi et al., 2018). Research from Nurmiati et al., 2024 said that, GPA medium is a medium used to see the total presence of microbes in the medium that allows all groups of microbes to grow. Treatment solutions were formulated to achieve soil improvement at levels that would meet project goals by considering results from previous small scale laboratory studies (DeJong et al., 2010). So far nutrient broth (Cuthbert et al., 2012) as the most common nutritional sources for the cultivation of the bacterium have been investigated by different researchers. However, these nutritional sources are uneconomical for large scale applications. Experimental biocementation consumes large amount

of fresh water and great amount of energy during preparation of distilled water and providing sterilization condition for culture media. Generally, in the traditional industries, the rate of wasted material is very high (Ipekçi et al., 2018; Kam et al., 2017, 2018). Thus, investigation of novel nutritional sources and also novel approaches are highly demanded.

Proteins are macro compounds that have an important role in life that function as biomolecules such as nucleoproteins, enzymes, hormones, antibodies and muscle contractions (Astuti et al., 2022). There are many industrial wastes rich in proteins, especially from the production, preparation and consumption of food that could be used as alternative nutrient sources in biotechnological processes. They could be hazardous to the environment if released in large quantities. However, if used effectively, they can be a valuable source of nutrients for different applications, providing a dual benefit through both cost reduction and environmental protection via waste recycling. Aside from the protein requirement (Whiffin 2004), urea is the other critical ingredient needed for *S. pasteurii* growth as well as for the ureolytic bio-induced calcite precipitation process. Waste rich in protein or commonly known as whey has a significant carbohydrate, protein and mineral content (Patel et al, 2016). When a large amount of whey is discarded as effluent it causes an environmental problem (Silva et al., 2009) and reduces dissolved oxygen and aquatic life as consequence (Aider et al., 2009).

According the result of the research from Oana et al., 2015, Whey, also called permeate, induced a bacterial enzymatic activity of about 80 % when compared to the reference nutrient medium, with a longer lag phase in the bacterial growth. Whey, followed by the alkaline water resulting from cleaning the installed systems of dairy factories, and LML, are potential candidates for use as a less expensive and low environmental impact nutrient source for biotechnological applications. The result of the research from Sandra et al.,2021, also revealed that Whey was successfully employed as an economical nutrient source for the growth of *Sporosarcina pasteurii* isolated from agricultural soils in Boyacá (Colombia). To the usual nutrient broth, various concentrations of whey were added. The increase in whey percentage in the culture media promoted calcite production with urea (30 g/L) and calcium chloride (30 g/L) at 200 rpm and 30 °C for 24 h. Whey addition in nutrient broth promoted calcite production and this type of crystal is more stable and has a higher density compared to vaterite.

Biocementation has become an alternative procedure in civil infrastructure by utilizing living things such as microorganisms. This alternative is not suitable for large-scale industries if the biocementation process uses cementation solutions such as nutrient broth, nutrient agar, urea, and calcium chloride. That being said, to optimize the culture, medium- and large-scale industries should utilize organic waste such as whey. Whey is the protein waste from many industries that can be easily found and is ecologically friendly. According to some research, whey can become a nutrient source for the growth of *S. pasteurii* with low cost and is simply the treatment process in biocementation. On account of this, whey can be an alternative component in optimizing the culture medium for the cultivation of *S. pasteurii*.

REFERENCES

- Aider, M., De Halleux, D., & Melnikova, I. (n.d.). Skim acidic milk whey cryoconcentration and assessment of its functional properties: Impact of processing conditions. *Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies/Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, 10(3), 334–341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifset.2009.01.005>
- Anbu P, Kang CH, Shin YJ, So JS. Formations of calcium carbonate minerals by bacteria and its multiple applications. (2016). *SpringerPlus*, 5:250.
- Astuti, Febria. Fitria M.J, Lia P.S. Diversifikasi Pengolahan Keripik yang Berbeda. (2022). Jurnal Perikanan Dan Kelautan, Volume 27 No. 2.**
- Cuthbert, M.O., Riley, M.S., Handley-Sidhu, S., Renshaw, J.C., Tobler, D.J., Phoenix, V.R., Mackay, R. Controls on the rate of ureolysis and the morphology of carbonate precipitated by *S. pasteurii* biofilms and limits due to bacterial encapsulation. (2010). *Ecol. Eng*, 41, 32e40.
- Cuzman, O. A., Richter, K., Wittig, L., & Tiano, P. (2015). Alternative nutrient sources for biotechnological use of *Sporosarcina pasteurii*. *World Journal of Microbiology & Biotechnology Incorporating the MIRCEN Journal of Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology/World Journal of Microbiology & Biotechnology*, 31(6), 897–906. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11274-015-1844-z>
- DeJong, J. T., Mortensen, B. M., Martinez, B. C., & Nelson, D. C. (2010). Bio-mediated soil improvement. *Ecological Engineering*, 36(2), 197–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2008.12.029>
- Gorospe CM, Han SH, Kim SG, Park JY, Kang CH, Jeong JH, So JS. Effects of different calcium salts on calcium carbonate crystal formation by *sporosarcina pasteurii* KCTC 3558. (2011). *Biotechnol Bioprocess Eng*, 18:903–8.
- Silva, M. F., Fornari, R. C., Mazutti, M. A., De Oliveira, D., Padilha, F. F., Cichoski, A. J., . . . Treichel, H. (2009). Production and characterization of xanthan gum by *Xanthomonas campestris* using cheese whey as sole carbon source. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 90(1), 119–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2008.06.010>
- Ipekçi, A., Kam, M., & Saruhan, H. (2018). Investigation of 3D printing occupancy rates effect on mechanical properties and surface roughness of PET-G material products. *Journal of New Results in Science*, 7(2), 1–8. Retrieved from <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/510498>
- Kam, M., Ipekçi, A., Saruhan, H. Investigation of 3D printing filling structures effect on mechanical properties and surface roughness of PET-G material products. (2017). *Gaziosmanpaşa, a Bilimsel Aras, Tirma Dergisi*, 6, 114e121.

Lauchnor EG, Topp DM, Parker AE, Gerlach R. Whole cell kinetics of urealy-sis by sporosarcina pasteurii. (2015). . *J Appl Microbiol*, 118:1321–32.

Nurmiati. Periadnadi. Sherly, J. Annisa, A. Eksplorasi bakteri-bakteri pemfermentasi dalam beberapa produk tempe di kota padang. (2024). *Bioscientist : Jurnal Ilmiah Biologi*, Volume 12(Issue 1).

Patel, A. K., Vaisnav, N., Mathur, A., Gupta, R., & Tuli, D. K. (2016). Whey waste as potential feedstock for biohydrogen production. *Renewable Energy*, 98, 221–225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2016.02.039>

Periadnadi, P., Sari, D. K., & Nurmiati, N. (2018). Isolasi dan keberadaan khamir potensial pemfermentasi nira aren (arenga pinnata merr.) Dari dataran rendah dan dataran tinggi di sumatera barat. *Bioeksperimen*, 4(1), 29–36. <https://doi.org/10.23917/bioeksperimen.v4i1.5927>

Prozorov, T. Bacterial magnetite biomineralization. (2014). *Semin. Cell Dev. Biol*, 46, 36–43.

Sandra, Chaparro,.. (2021). Whey as an Alternative Nutrient Medium for Growth of Sporosarcina pasteurii and Its Effect on CaCO₃ Polymorphism and Fly Ash Bioconsolidation. *Materials*, 14(10), 2470. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14102470>

Spiesz, E. M., Schmieden, D. T., Grande, A. M., Liang, K., Schwiedrzik, J., Natalio, F., . . . Meyer, A. S. (2019). Bacterially produced, Nacre-Inspired composite materials. *Small*, 15(22). <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.201805312>

Wong, L.S. Microbial cementation of ureolytic bacteria from the genus bacillus: A review of the bacterial application on cement-based materials for cleaner production. (2019). *J. Clean. Prod*, 93, 5e17.

Whiffin, V. S. (2008). *Microbial CACO₃ precipitation: for the production of biocement*. Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/11231035.pdf>

Zhu T, Dittrich M. Carbonate precipitation through microbial activities in natural environment, and their potential in biotechnology: a review. (2015). *Front Bioeng Biotechnol*, 4:4.